

DEMOGRAPHIC DEVELOPMENT OF RURAL SETTLEMENTS

Introdução

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Introdução

- *The research deals with the definition of demographic development of rural settlements of Ukraine and Brazil in the context of social transformation processes.*
- *The purpose of the research is to determine modern trends and priority directions of demographic development of rural areas.*

Introdução

- The subject of the analysis –
- demographic changes (mainly the process of depopulation, aging of the population, foreign migration),
- improvement of living conditions (equipping households with elements of technical infrastructure, access to public services, transport accessibility),
- analysis of the deagrarianisation process (decreasing role of agricultural livelihoods rural areas, as well as employment in agriculture),
- analysis of the non-agricultural sector (the non-agricultural labor market for the rural areas residents) and the agricultural sector (changes in the agrarian structure)
- the characteristics of the labor market situation in rural areas (employment, unemployment).

Procedimientos Adotados.

Analyzing the demographic potential of rural areas it is necessary to emphasize that the size of the population, especially that part of it that is engaged in the production process, is a decisive factor in the socio-economic development of the country,

therefore, demographic problems should be subject to proper theoretical understanding, constant macro-level monitoring and to be decided at the level of strategic state priorities.

A clear understanding of the socio-demographic characteristics of the population, problems and prospects for their development is important for forecasting and planning effective social policy of the state.

Preservation of the population and improvement of its qualitative characteristics can be one of the strategic directions for the state.

The positive socio-demographic structure of the population makes it possible to ensure the protection of the main spheres of national security and, accordingly, to ensure their sustainable development.

Resultados e discussão.

Socio-demographic risks are inertial in nature, and therefore are the most strategically dangerous, as they irreversibly deform the structure of society.

Socio-demographic processes in the village of Ukraine have their own specific characteristics, due to several factors:

Beginning in 1991, the main factor in the continuous reduction of the rural population is depopulation.

Depopulation has become a fundamental factor in the acceleration of the aging population, which is the most significant feature of long-term changes in its gender and age composition.

The load on the working age population as persons of working age and after-working age in villages is significantly higher than in cities and from normative indicators.

A characteristic feature of the migration situation in the countryside is the constant predominance of the outflow of population over the arrivals.

Because of the long-term outflow of young people, the reduction of its demographic and labour potential was due to the loss of the most productive in the demographic and economic terms of the population.

Resultados e discussão.

Migration movement is also added to the decline of the rural population: domestic, interregional and interstate, which is an accurate indicator of the economic and social situation in the country.

It has been established that migration plays a dominant role in the formation of human resources, which in recent years has been intensively developed and considered by us as the main cause of the social decline of the peasantry, the main destructive force of the demographic basis of its social rebirth.

Resultados e discussão.

When studying the socio-demographic problems we focus not only on quantitative changes in demographic development indicators, but also on the factors that shape them.

Thus, studies of the correlation between

- the average annual number of employees in agriculture*
- and the indicators of the volume of migration flows (in the coefficients of arrival and departure) of different directions and levels at the beginning of the current century*

confirmed the strengthening of the connection between the reduction of employees in the industry and the processes of leaving the countryside.

An almost complete functional relationship is observed between the coefficients of arrival in rural areas and rural employment.

Resultados e discussão.

Among the global problems of humanity that need to be taken into account when drawing up a development strategy for both the country and its regions, special attention should be paid to those that lie in the social plane.

These include, in particular, the problems of ensuring demographic security, and the problems of population depopulation, which are characterized by low birth rates and high mortality, as well as a high degree of demographic burden of the disabled population to workable.

Resultados e discussão.

The conceptual idea of building a system of indicators for assessing the level of demographic safety is to combine the study of the main demographic processes (natural and mechanical reproduction of the population), the structural characteristics of the population, as well as qualitative parameters from which to separate the health of the population and the spread of socially dangerous diseases.

Considerações Finais.

The main mechanism of demographic development is the development and implementation of targeted programs for solving individual problems.

Need to be taken into account when developing a strategy for the development of both the country and its regions to assess the state of demographic security system of indicators.

It is necessary to develop not only threshold values, which are the beginning of negative destructive changes in the demographic system, but also target benchmarks that represent the strategic goals of individual components of demographic security.

Considerações Finais.

In order to find the best models, it is advisable to take into account the experience of foreign countries and develop their own set of instruments in the field of state regulation of demographic processes in accordance with the defined goals and priorities of demographic development.

The conceptual approach, which provides for the separation of the state regulation of the sphere of development of rural areas, will make it possible to direct resources to solve the socio-demographic problems of the rural areas.

A stylized illustration of a landscape. In the foreground, there are rolling green hills. On the left, a purple and pink flower with a brown stem and small orange leaves grows on a hill. The background features blue wavy hills under a light blue sky.

Agradecimientos.